

The Effect of Father Involvement Towards the Tendency of Delinquent Behavior among Adolescents in Batak Toba Ethnic

Fadhilah, Cut Rafyqa¹; Sutatminingsih, Raras²; Marini, Liza³

¹Departement of Clinical Psychology, University of Sumatera Utara, Medan, Indonesia, 20155

²Departement of Clinical Psychology, University of Sumatera Utara, Medan, Indonesia, 20155

³Departement of Clinical Psychology, University of Sumatera Utara, Medan, Indonesia, 20155

Abstract— The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of father involvement towards the tendency of delinquent behavior among adolescents in Batak Toba ethnic. This study uses a nonprobability sampling technique and the total number of samples was 161 Batak Toba adolescent in Medan city with the age ranging from 15 to 18 years old. The data were collected using father involvement scale and the tendency of delinquent behavior scale. The methodology of data analysis used in this study is a simple regression method. The results showed that father involvement has an effect towards the tendency of delinquent behavior among adolescents in Batak Toba ethnic. This research showed that higher their involvement, the lower the tendency of delinquent behavior rate of adolescents in Batak Toba ethnic and vice versa.

Keywords— Adolescent, father involvement, delinquent behavior.

I. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is a country with rich cultures which are dependent on existing ethnic. One of the existing and dominating ethnic is from the northern side of Sumatera Island, including in the capital city Medan namely Batak Toba (Encyclopedia of Indonesian Ethnic Group, 1997).

Harahap and Siahaan (1987) stated that the people of Batak Toba ethnic orient themselves to the values of *Hamoraon* (wealth), *Hagabeon* (ancestry), *Hasangapon* (honor), kinship of *dalihan na tolu*, religion, *Hamajouan* (advancement), *law/patik dohat uhum*, conflict, and protection, which becomes their faith, honor, and dream of lives. However, among those values, ancestry/descendant (*hagabeon*) becomes the most important. A study conducted by Irmawati (2007) showed that the 3H values (*hamoraon*, *hagabeon*, and *hasangapon*) along with the kinship of *dalihan na tolu*, religion, *hamajouan* (advancement), *law/patik dohat uhum*, and protection play important roles.

The philosophy of life believed by this ethnic is unique, and this includes the parenting aspect, which puts a huge hope on children to the value of *hagabeon*. This is due to their belief in the kinship system of patrilineal principle (Harahap and Siahaan, 1987). In the family system of Batak Toba ethnic, mothers are an important source of strength. It is common to see them working very hard by taking up responsibilities outside and on the other side in order to deal with other house needs including parenting. Mothers in Batak Toba ethnic acquire numerous attentions from the whole family, from being able to provide posterity to both son and

daughter and being able to educate the children to be a successful (Maulina and Sutatminingsih, 2005; Rahmah, 2012). The result of a study conducted by Irmawati (2007) found that their role and devotion are dominant as they live up the spirit and become role models to their children. They (mothers) are ready to give everything for the sake of their children success.

However, fathers of the Batak Toba ethnic play the roles of breadwinners and custom doers by working from morning to evening. Families in Batak Toba are strongly holding onto the kinship system of patrilineal principles therefore fathers have to introduce and pass down parenting customs and cultures to their children. They are the breadwinners while mothers take the responsibility of parenting. In addition, father also depicted as negative figures since they have a habit to ask for money, go drinking and stay at *tuak* (palm wine) shop. These habits make them waste their spare time outside the house than inside with the family (Irmawati, 2007).

Based on the explanation above, fathers play a minor role in parenting their children, while mothers are dominant. In contrast to the above condition, many current research, shows that their involvement in parenting is currently giving positive impact on children. It also reduces bad behavior of adolescents, such as drug usage, delinquent, and other acts of violence (Zimmerman, Salem, and Notaro, 2000; Volker, 2014). Barnes (1992) also added that the involvement of fathers in parenting reduces the rate of skipping class and stealing. A study conducted by Zuhairah and Tatar (2017) in Banda Aceh showed a negative yet significant relation between father involvement and teenage delinquent with the ability to reduce them.

Related to the above explanation, it could be seen that there is an impact of father involvement towards the tendency of delinquent behavior. Therefore, this study aims to determine the effect of father involvement towards the tendency of delinquent behavior among adolescents in Batak Toba ethnic.

II. METHODS

This study using *non-probability sampling* technique type *availability*. Data were obtained from the targeted population based on availability, coincidental condition, study simplicity, and the source compatibility (Daniel, 2012). The Batak Toba

adolescents involved in this study were 161 aged 15-18 years old using the scale of father involvement and the tendency of delinquent behavior.

The scale of father involvement was arranged based on their involvement as stated by Pleck and Lamb (2010). The scale used was a Likert model with four answers which were Always, Frequently, Rarely, and Never. Meanwhile the scale of the tendency of delinquent behavior was arranged based on the categories and kinds of delinquent behavior as stated by Bynum and Thompson (2001). The scale was Likert scale with four answers were Very appropriate, Appropriate, Not Inappropriate, and Very Inappropriate.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The analysis method used in this study was a simple regression method using SPSS for windows version 23. Before analyzing the data, the assumption test was conducted which comprised of normality and linearity test. The result of hypothesis tests as shown below:

TABEL I. Analysis of the Effect of Father Involvement towards the Tendency of Delinquent Behavior

Model	R	R Square	F	Sig.
1	.392 ^a	.153	28.812	.000

Based on the analysis result above, the significant effect of father involvement in the rate of the tendency of delinquent behavior among adolescents in Batak Toba Ethnic is $F = 28.812$, $p < 0.05$. Besides, the determinant coefficient rate (R^2) of 0.153, shows that the effect of father involvement towards the tendency of delinquent behavior was 15.3% while the rest (84.7%) was caused by other factors not observed in this study. Furthermore, the analysis of the regression equation showed that father involvement gave a negative rate which means a higher rate of involvement tends to lower the delinquent fate of adolescents.

The father involvement also affected the development of adolescents, as their attention and support gives feeling of acceptance, attention, and confidence is a good sign of development (Sarwono, 2010). The positive perception of adolescents towards father involvement emotionally indicates a good and close relationship and feeling of love which tends to avoid sadness and disappointment. The fathers involved in their children's lives, particularly in education and social intercourse tend to increase their social skill. Their involvement tends to affect their relationship and academic achievement. It also helps them to develop, control and adapt to their environment (Flouri and Buchanan, 2003). Fathers give a direct impact through behaviors, attitudes, and messages, with an indirect impact based on how they treat other people (Lamb, 2010).

The explanation above was in line with families in Batak Toba ethnic where fathers acted as the breadwinners and custom doers. It became the reason why they pass the values of the Batak Toba ethnic to their children both in daily activities and formal occasions (Gultom, 1992).

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the result of the analysis, it could be concluded that the involvement of father gave a negative effect towards the tendency of delinquent behavior among adolescents in Batak Toba ethnic with a percentage of 15.3%. It showed that higher their involvement, the lower the delinquent rate of adolescents in Batak Toba ethnic and vice versa.

V. SUGGESTION

1. Limiting the subject of study to be more specific. For example, adolescents with a background in carrying out delinquent activities or those counseled by teachers.
2. Studying the variable of delinquent behavior in one specific gender, such as focusing to conduct the study on male or female students.
3. Father's from the Batak Toba or any other ethnic, should directly involve themselves in their children's lives for them to feel some sense of attention thereby, building a good relationship between them.

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